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CLINICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF CERVICAL INTRAEPITHELIAL NEOPLASIA ASSOCIATED WITH PAPILLOMAVIRUS INFECTION

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ABSTRACT

Despite modern progress in the diagnosis and treatment of cervical diseases, its pathology remains a major problem for both theoretical medicine and practical gynecology. The number of patients with cervical cancer continues to grow, and therefore the relevance of this problem is of particular importance. One of the reasons for the development of cervical cancer is the highly oncogenic type of human papillomaviruses. The article discusses the clinical and morphological features of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia associated with human papillomavirus. The presented material describes the clinical changes that occur in women with cervical intraepithelial neoplasia caused by human papillomavirus, the nature of their progression, and the causes of their origin.

Keywords: Human papillomavirus (HPV), cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN), clinical and morphological features, prognosis.

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КЛИНИКО-МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЦЕРВИКАЛЬНЫХ ИНТРАЭПИТЕЛИАЛЬНЫХ НЕОПЛАЗИЙ, АССОЦИИРОВАННЫХ С ПАПИЛЛОМАВИРУСНОЙ ИНФЕКЦИЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Несмотря на современные успехи в диагностике и лечении заболеваний шейки матки, ее патология остается серьезной проблемой как для теоретической медицины, так и для практической гинекологии. Количество больных раком шейки матки продолжает расти, в связи с чем актуальность данной проблемы приобретает особое значение. Одной из причин развития рака шейки матки является высокоонкогенный тип вирусов папилломы человека. В статье обсуждаются клинико-морфологические особенности цервикальной интраэпителиальной неоплазии, ассоциированной с вирусом папилломы человека. В представленном материале описаны клинические изменения, возникающие у женщин с цервикальной интраэпителиальной неоплазией, вызванной вирусом папилломы человека, характер их прогрессирования и причины возникновения.

Ключевые слова: Папилломавирусы человека (ПВЧ), цервикальная интраэпителиальная неоплазия, клинико-морфологические особенности, прогноз.

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INSON PAPILOMAVIRUSI BILAN KECHUVCHI SERVIKAL INTRAEPITELIAL NEOPLAZIYANING KLINIK-MORFOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Bachadon bo'yni kasalliklarini tashxislash va davolashda zamonaviy yutuqlarga erishilganiga qaramay, uning patologiyasi ham nazariy tibbiyot, ham amaliy ginekologiya uchun asosiy muammo bo'lib qolmoqda. Bachadon bo'yni saratoni bilan og'rikan bemorlar soni o'sishda davom etmoqda va shuning uchun bu muammoning dolzarbligi alohida ahamiyatga ega. Bachadon bo'yni saratoni rivojlanishining sabablaridan biri bu yuqori onkogen tipdagi inson papilloma viruslaridir. Maqolada inson papillomavirusi bilan birga kechuvchi bachadon bo'yni intraepitelial neoplaziyaning klinik-morfologik xususiyatlari muhokama qilingan. Taqdim etilgan materialda Inson papillomavirusi bilan kechuvchi servikal intraepitelial neoplaziya bor ayollarda yuzaga keladigan klinik o'zgarishlar, ularning kechish xarakteri, ularning kelib chiqish sabablari aks ettirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Inson papillomavirusi, servikal intraepitelial neoplaziyasi, klinik-morfologik xususiyat, prognoz

Relevance. Every year in the world more than 570 thousand women are diagnosed with cervical cancer (BBC), which is 6.6% of the total system of malignant tumors. It is the fourth most common cancer in women and kills 311,000 people every year. Cervical intraepithelial neoplasias occur due to the persistence of human papilloma virus (OPV) with high carcinogenic risk and "...is an urgent problem of reproductive medicine, leading to the development of BBC for several years and decades..." 1. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the average annual increase in OPV is two and a half to three million. The rate of asymptomatic virus transmission is high worldwide, in Russia - 15.5%; USA - 28.6%; In Europe - 2-12%. 70% of cases of development of BBS are caused by OPV types 16 and 18. The average age of those diagnosed with cervical cancer (BBC) is 49 years. Over the last 50 years, in developed countries, "...the introduction of Pap smear and OPV vaccination has reduced morbidity and mortality by 75%..." 2. Thus, despite the widespread implementation of preventive measures, the development and implementation of new methods of early diagnosis and treatment of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN) are urgent. Searching for sensitive specific markers of diagnosis, risk of development, examination algorithm and treatment of neoplastic changes of cervical epithelium and prevention of oncological transformation of cervical epithelium remains one of the urgent problems of modern gynecology. In the world, special attention is paid to scientific research aimed at improving the pathogenetic basis of diagnosis, treatment and preventive measures of cervical pre-cancerous diseases in women. A global strategy to accelerate the elimination of BBS has been developed, which includes three main components: vaccination, screening and treatment. Successful implementation of all three components would reduce new cases of the disease by 40% in 2050 and prevent 5 million disease-related deaths. 194 countries of the world have committed to eliminate BBC disease within the framework of the adopted decision.

In our country, comprehensive reforms are being carried out in the development of the medical field, adaptation of the medical system to the requirements of world standards, early detection of oncological diseases among women, development of preventive methods and improvement of treatment methods. «...increasing the effectiveness, quality and popularity of medical care provided to the population in our country, as well as forming a system of medical standardization, introducing high-tech methods of diagnosis and treatment, creating effective models of patronage service and dispensary, supporting a healthy lifestyle and preventing diseases priority tasks such as prevention...» 3 are defined. Based on this, diagnosis of cervical cancer pre-diseases in women, pathogenetic justification of treatment-prophylactic measures is considered one of the urgent directions.

According to the World Health Organization, CIN is a disease of the cervix associated with OPV-infection, which is an important problem of modern gynecology due to the fact that OPV-infection has been proven to undergo oncological transformation (Attoeva D.I. with co-ed., 2019; Afanaseva N.A co-ed., 2019; Bayramova G.R., 2018; Campos-Viguri

G.E. et al., 2015). The importance of the problem of non-specific pathology of the cervix is aggravated by its "rejuvenation" (Gumilevskaya O.P. with co-ed., 2016; Gumilevsky B. Yu. with co-ed., 2019; Drukh V.M. with co-ed., 2015; Fu W et al., 2016).

In the emergence and development of this pathology, the combination of OPV infection with a high oncogenic risk virus and the development of the neoplastic process of the cervical epithelium of various severity indicate an important homeostatic system dysregulation of the body - an increase in the activity of oncogenic proteins, a violation of the endocrine balance, a decrease in immune protection, and a disruption of the intercellular cellular matrix (Dultseva T.S. with co-ed., 2010; Dufinets I.E., 2019; Zabela A.V. with co-ed., 2018; Zadiashvili M.D. with co-ed., 2017; Ebisch R.M. et al., 2016).

HPV is a highly contagious DNA-containing virus that has a number of features: it is an epithelial type of virus that infects the skin and mucous membranes; is an anthroponotic infection; associated with oncological diseases – can cause cervical cancer (CC), anal cancer, anogenital warts, laryngeal papillomatosis, etc.

More than 200 HPV types have been described so far. Depending on the type of HPV, it has a high or low oncogenic potential. According to the oncogenic danger to humans, types of HPV are distinguished.

- with high oncogenic potential (16, 18, 26, 31, 33, 35, 39, 45, 51, 52, 53, 56, 58, 59, 66, 68, 73, 82), which cause neoplastic processes and are the cause occurrence of cervical cancer;
- with low oncogenic potential (6, 11, 40, 42, 43, 44, 54, 61, 72, 81), which cause benign changes, anogenital warts.

HPV-associated pathology manifests itself most in a variety of forms. Clinical classification HPV-associated lower genital lesions include.

- Clinical forms (visible to the naked eye):
 - exophytic warts.
 - Subclinical forms (invisible to the naked eye) eye, asymptomatic, detected only during colposcopy and / or cytological, histological examination):
 - flat warts (typical structure with multiple koilocytes);
 - small forms (various changes in the multilayer squamous and metaplastic epithelium with single koilocytes);
 - inverted warts with localization in crypts;
 - Condylomatous cervicitis and vaginitis.
 - Latent forms (detection of HPV DNA by molecular methods without morphological signs of papillomavirus infection - PVI).
 - Cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN) and cervical cancer.
 - Intraepithelial neoplasia and other cancers.

Cervical intraepithelial neoplasia is one of the most important problems in modern gynecology. From a clinical and morphological point of view, dysplasia is a violation of differentiation, maturation, aging and apoptosis of epithelial cells lining the cervix. Depending on the severity of dysplastic changes, morphologically, mild (CIN I), moderate (CIN II) and severe (CIN III) dysplasia are distinguished. CIN I is characterized by polymorphism of cellular elements with

pronounced hyperchromicity of the nuclei and a high nuclear-cytoplasmic ratio, with the involvement of a third of the stratified squamous epithelium. In the case of CIN II, cellular atypism and numerous mitoses are determined. CIN III is characterized by cellular atypism. According to the WHO classification (1982) and Bethesda (2001, 2004, 2014), the concepts of severe dysplasia and cancer in situ are combined into one pathological process (CIN III and HSIL) [3,4,5].

According to the world literature, by the end of the 20th century, more than 30 million women were identified with low-risk cervical lesions and more than 10 million high-risk. Thus, in the United States, the prevalence of precancer of the cervix in the age group of 25-29 years is about 800 cases per 100,000 women. Of these, CIN 2-3 accounts for about 150 cases per 100,000 women. Abnormal cytological smears for women of all ages are an order of magnitude higher and account for 7800 cases per 100,000 women. According to Russian researchers in Russia, squamous intraepithelial lesions of the cervix in the structure of gynecological morbidity in women of reproductive age vary from 10.7% to 38.8%. Given the fact of the possible oncotransformation of squamous intraepithelial lesions of the cervix, the prevalence of cervical cancer is an important indicator of the organization of primary health care. Scientists Zheng B. et al. (2017) studied 2,206,588 women aged 15 to 88 years (mean age 38.4 years), of whom 37,895 had a cytological result for LSIL. According to the results of the study, it was found that LSIL was detected in women aged 30 (2.1% and 1.7%, respectively), that is, with an increase in the age of women, the number of detected LSIL significantly decreases. In 75.8% of cases, women with LSIL were HPV positive, but their number significantly decreased with increasing age of the patients, with the exception of women over 60 years of age. In 2008, McCredie published the only New Zealand clinical trial known to date, in which 92 women with a histologically verified diagnosis of CIN 3 received no treatment but only follow-up. According to the results of this study, cervical cancer after 10 years developed in 31% of women, after 30 years - in 50% of observed women. According to a number of other authors, CIN 2-3 regresses to 30%, CIN 3 progresses to invasive cervical carcinoma from 0.2 to 0.4% within 12 months. According to Bruni L et al. (2015), the risk of cervical cancer in the world among women over 15 years of age is 2645.080 million cases annually. Of these, more than 527,000 develop cervical cancer. Despite advances in modern medicine, mortality from cervical cancer remains high. Thus, the average annual incidence of cervical cancer in the European Union is 13.2 cases per 100 thousand women, and the mortality rate is 5.9 cases per 100 thousand women per year. The lowest incidence is observed in the countries of Northern Europe, in Finland it is 3.6 cases, and in Sweden 8.0 cases per 100 thousand of the female population are registered [39]. In the Russian Federation in 2015, the number of new cases of cervical cancer was 16,710, the death rate was 5.39 cases per 100,000 women per year. In the age group of 15-39 years, the number of new cases was 3890, in the group of 40-44 years - 2128 cases [14]. One of the highest incidence rates of cervical cancer is observed in developing countries: in Haiti it is 93.8 cases, in Zimbabwe - 67.2, in Tanzania - 61.4 cases per 100,000 female population [39]. From 1980 to 2010 Forouzanfar et al. (2011) studied the age of women with cervical cancer annually in 187 countries. The study found that the incidence of cervical cancer globally increased from 378,000 cases per year in 1980 to 454,000 cases per year in 2010 (an annual increase of 0.6%). Cervical cancer deaths are declining, but in 2010 the incidence was still 200,000 deaths. In developing countries, 46,000 of these women were aged 15-49 and 109,000 were aged 50 or older [77].

The purpose of clinical research.

Determination of the prognostic value of clinical and morphological features in patients with cervical intraepithelial neoplasia with human papillomavirus.

Materials and research methods.

The study was retrospectively and prospectively analyzed by women diagnosed with cervical intraepithelial neoplasia with human papillomavirus in the "Family and Marriage Counseling Polyclinic" RIAGIATM DM.

Entry criteria:

Age from 30 to 49 years

Patients with morphologically confirmed moderate cervical intraepithelial dysplasia

Exclusion criteria:

The postpartum period

During the decompensation stage, kidney, liver, and lung function disorders

Bleeding in the genitals

Pregnancy

Oncological diseases

A retrospective and prospective analysis was conducted in order to study the clinical and morphological characteristics of patients with cervical intraepithelial neoplasia caused by human papillomavirus. Ambulatory anamnesis of 45 women of childbearing age, aged 30 to 49 years, was reviewed. Of these, 30 women were analyzed retrospectively, and 15 women were prospectively analyzed.

Based on the purpose of our study, patients were divided into 2 groups. Of these, 30 women were CIN 2 human papillomavirus positive, and 15 were CIN 2 human papillomavirus negative.

Life history, reproductive and gynecological anamnesis, complaints, reproductive function, social status, duration of the disease, genetic predisposition to oncological pathology, contraceptive methods, the time of the beginning of sexual life and the number of sexual partners, harmful habits, i.e. smoking, the presence and severity of somatic pathology were studied. Visual examination of the cervix, cytological, bacteriological and PCR examinations of sexually transmitted infections, oncocytological examination of smears taken from the cervix, ultrasound examinations of the pelvic organs and calculation of colposcopic indicators were carried out in the mirrors.

Colposcopic results were evaluated using the International Federation of Colposcopy and Cervical Pathology (IFCPC) classification revised by the IFCPC Nomenclature Committee at the World Congress in Barcelona in June 2002. The obtained results were adapted to the International classification of colposcopy terms (2011, July, Rio de Janeiro).

In the research program, patients were studied based on an extended examination. Retrospective and prospective investigations were conducted as follows.

1. First visit:

1. Inquiry (anamnesis and complaints);
- 1.2. Checking in mirrors;
- 1.3. Ultrasound examination of small pelvic organs;
- 1.4. Bacterial examination;
- 1.5. Cytological examination;
- 1.6. Colposcopic examination;
- 1.7. Blood PCR examination;
- 1.8. OPV-cervical mucus;
- 1.9. Examination by doctors;

2. Second visit:

- 2.1. Examination, anamnesis results, UTT, cytological and bacteriological sowing of small pelvic organs, blood PCR and cervical mucus analysis;
- 2.2. Narrow specialist vision (oncologist, endocrinologist, oncogynecologist);
- 2.3. Analysis of the conclusions of profile specialists and their study and drawing up a treatment plan based on the conclusions obtained.

Results and experimental discussion

Examination of patients was carried out according to a single scheme, including an assessment of the data of the general and obstetric-gynecological anamnesis, general clinical, gynecological examination and special research methods.

Each group was analyzed based on the above-mentioned tests. 30 women were CIN 2 human papillomavirus positive and 15 women were CIN 2 human papillomavirus negative. The following results were obtained from the survey (history and complaints): genital discharge. Pain, itching and soreness in the labia.

Information about the generative history, %: I and II infertility - 25.2%, Repeated pregnant - 90.2%, Repeated births - 26%, Spontaneous miscarriage - 14.8%, Non-developing pregnancy - 24.1%, Ectopic pregnancy - 5, 8%, 1-2 medical abortions - 4.1%, 3 or more medical abortions - 1.2%.

Information about contraceptive methods, %: IUD, Condoms - 27.9%, calendar method - 4.2%, coitus interruptus - 5.0%, were not protected - 62.9%.

Information about past somatic diseases, %: frequent acute respiratory viral infections - 31.5%, bronchitis - 5.6%, pneumonia - 2.8%, gastritis - 7.4%, colitis - 2.2%, hepatitis A - 14.8, ICD - 15.7%, frequent cystitis - 20%.

Painful menstruation, pain in the lower abdomen and lower back. In the ultrasound examination of the pelvic organs, uterine body endometriosis - 14%, uterine myoma - 12%, right-sided ovarian cyst - 6%, left-sided ovarian cyst - 8% and other types of changes - 16% UTT without changes - 44%.

For cytological examination of cervical smears, which was performed in all patients, the material was taken using cytobrush brushes, followed by its fixation. Slides were stained by Papanicolaou. The evaluation of the results was carried out in accordance with the terminological system of Bethesda (2001), which allows to establish the degree of SIL (LSIL, HSIL).

Extended colposcopy was performed in all patients to visually scan cervical tissue under a microscope in response to treatment with 3% acetic acid and 2% Lugol's solution.

The international classification of colposcopic terms (2003) was applied. To unify the results obtained, the clinical colposcopic classification

(M. Shafi and S. Nazeer, 2006) was used with the calculation of the clinical colposcopic index (in points). When abnormal colposcopic pictures were detected, a targeted biopsy of the exocervix and/or scrapings of the endocervix was performed.

The assessment of the infectious status of the cervix was carried out by means of molecular biological and microbiological studies at the Center for Laboratory Diagnostics. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) of

cervical scrapings was performed to detect high (16, 18, 31, 33, 35, 39, 45, 52, 58, 59, 67) and low (6.11) oncogenic risk HPV.

The amount of HPV DNA types 16 and 18 was determined by real-time PCR. Detection of Chlamydia trachomatis, Mycoplasma genitalium, herpes simplex virus type 1 and type II, cytomegalovirus was carried out by PCR. Microbiological examination of cervical and vaginal discharge was performed in the microbiological laboratory of the Central Research Laboratory. All patients underwent quantitative bacteriological culture for microflora (for dysbiosis) and sensitivity to antibiotics with a quantitative determination of opportunistic and normal vaginal microflora.

In the structure of contraceptive methods, there was a predominant predominance of irregular barrier contraception in the 1st and 2nd groups (p=0.039, p=0.005) or its absence. The nonspecific nature of complaints from the genitals did not have statistically significant differences in patients of the studied groups. The presented anamnestic data confirm not only the role of social factors (features of sexual behavior, smoking, the nature of contraception) in the development of CIN against the background of papillomavirus infection (G.N. Minkina, I.B. Manukhin, 2001, S.I. Collins et al. 2005, B.I. Stefănescu et al. 2007), but also their influence on the severity of the process. The microbiological section of the study made it possible to establish the qualitative and quantitative component of HIV testing of the cervix. Both in the 1st and 2nd groups, the presence of HPV of high oncogenic risk was found with a predominance of HPV type 16 (48.0 and 69.0%, respectively, p=0.045) in the variant of mono-infection or combined infection with HPV type 18 (p>0.05) (Fig. 3). For patients of the 1st group, along with the dominance of HPV type 16, a high frequency of other types of high-risk HPV was characteristic, in contrast to patients of the 2nd group of patients (p = 0.023). Combined infection of the cervix with high-risk HPV and HPV type 6 was found in patients of the 1st (8.2%) and 2nd (4.7%) groups (p=0.74).

HPV types of high oncogenic risk in patients with CIN2, %

The level of viral load of HPV type 16.18 in patients with CIN 2

Among the HPV associates in the cervicovaginal biotope, BII, C. trachomatis, Candida spp., Ureaplasma urealyticum, Mycoplasma hominis, G. vaginalis were identified both in a clinically significant titer

and in a titer of less than 10⁶ CFU/ml in the absence of statistically significant differences between the main groups.

Results of histological studies of cervical biopsts

Cervicitis was 36%, endocervicitis and cervicitis in 38%, endocervicitis and cervicitis with condyloma in 13%, polyp and cervicitis in 13% according to the results of histological examination of cervical biopsies.

Cases of the absence of STIs and dysbiosis noted in the comparison group were observed much more often (44%) than in the 1st group (68%) and in the 2nd (7.1%, p=0.000) group.

Comparative analysis of colposcopy data in patients with CIN revealed frequent registration of abnormal colposcopic signs that dominated in various combinations in the 2nd group ($p=0.03$), with a high frequency of the symptom of uneven iodine-positive epithelium in the 1st and 2nd groups ($p>0.05$) in contrast to the comparison group ($X^2Yates=17.44$, $p=0.000$).

Signs of inflammation were observed in every 3 cases and did not have statistically significant differences depending on the presence of HPV. To objectify the obtained data, a clinical and colposcopic analysis was performed taking into account the age of patients, smoking, cytology data, the degree of whitening of the epithelium after acetic acid, the surface area of the lesion, with an assessment of the intercapillary distance, focality of the lesion and the nature of the surface (M.Shafi, S.Nazeer, 2006).

After scoring the clinical and colposcopic index, we found an increase in its value in the 2nd group relative to the 1st group and the comparison group ($p=0.000$) (Fig. 5). In patients with CIN I in the 1st group and the comparison group, no dependence of its values on the presence of HPV was found ($p>0.05$).

The level of clinical-colposcopic index correlated with the level of viral load of HPV type 16 ($r=0.4$, $p=0.01$).

Summary

1. Patients with HPV-related cervical intraepithelial neoplasia are characterized by a predominance of HPV type 16: 69% high-grade lesions (CINII), other types of HPV lesions account for 12%. Oncogenic risk HPV (type 16,18) virus load level affects the degree of damage. High loading (61.2%) predominates in CINII, the increase in the frequency of medium (48.2%) and low (12.2%) loading is statistically significant in CINII.

2. Cervical lesions associated with HPV are characterized by a high clinical-colposcopic index in CIN II.

3. In patients with high-grade HPV secondary lesions (CINII), the immunohistochemical indicator of rib4a in exocervical epithelium increases 3-fold - 6.0 (5.0; 7.0), which is associated with the level of HPV type 16 viral load.

4. If there is a correlation between the level of intraepithelial neoplasia of the cervix and the level of serum IFN- γ (in contrast to IL-4) ($t=0.45$; $p=0.04$), activation of interferonogenesis is not observed depending on the level of damage, which indicates the duration of papillomavirus infection able to maintain.

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